

Co creating a Feedback Culture in a Healthcare organization in the Caribbean

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ABSTRACT: A culture of feedback is crucial for the achievement of quality, especially of high-quality client centred care. Healthcare management then feels the need to support teams in the development of a robust feedback culture, for example by providing teams with feedback training. That is even more important in a multicultural, multilingual small island community. However, what kind of a feedback culture does staff need? Especially if teams consist of members from different cultures, different ages and gender? Management needs to involve staff in the co creation process of a quality feedback culture.

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This research presents the results of a case study of a secondary healthcare institute in the Caribbean. In the framework of a process of co-creating a feedback culture in every team of the organization a survey was conducted on the desired feedback culture of the staff members. In total 81 healthcare staff members from seven teams filled in the questionnaire. The questionnaire revealed -opposite to what the management expected- that there were little differences in the desired feedback culture in the healthcare organization, when you look at age or place of birth. This is interesting, because it gives the management the opportunity to focus on generic aspects of a sound feedback culture, rather than having to diversify to age or culture.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A culture of quality is crucial for any organization. The question is what we mean when we talk about a quality culture. Van Kemenade (1) studied definitions of quality culture in the non-profit sector especially higher education. He states that: "Quality culture is the dynamic, mostly emergent process of feeling responsible and taking collective ownership of your work or task" (1, page 162). Such a quality culture requires supporting information and feedback systems. For instance, in healthcare a culture of feedback is crucial for the quality of care. This is even more important on small islands, where resource constraints and close-knit communities amplify the impact of both successes and shortcomings. Sint Maarten is such an island in the Caribbean, part of which was a former Dutch colony, the other part is still French. The Dutch side has about 42.000 inhabitants (in 2023). Sint Maarten has a small, but very diverse (multilingual, multicultural) population. Secondary care there is provided by the hospital Sint Maarten Medical Centre (SMMC). It offers outpatient and inpatient services. Other main secondary care providers include the community-based mental health services from the Mental Health Foundation and the White and Yellow Cross Care Foundation (WYCCF). WYCCF has three departments. Sint Maarten's Home, that provides nursing home care, elderly care, psychogeriatric care, rehabilitation and a hospice; Sister Basilia Centre that has a Residence, Day Activity Centre, Home Care guidance and Guided Living and District Nursing that provides nursing care, home care and maternity care. It is the only facility for such services on the island. The White and Yellow Cross Care Foundation (WYCCF) values Client Centred Care. The organisation wants to provide 'care that is organized around the client'. To achieve that quality of care, a quality culture and especially a feedback culture is considered to be crucial.

A robust culture of feedback ensures that services align with unique community needs. Patient feedback is a prerequisite for client centred care and a feedback-rich environment reduces medical staff turnover by making employees feel valued. Since healthcare

teams are often limited in size and resources on the island, a strong feedback culture enables open communication and continuous learning among staff. However, one can and should not force a feedback culture upon staff. It can more easily emerge from a co-creation process wherein staff is involved. The WYCCF started a project to achieve this. As part of the project all staff members follow a one-day workshop ‘co-creating a feedback culture’. In that workshop a questionnaire is provided on the feedback culture the team member’s desire. This research supports that development process and reports on the results of that survey.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research presented here is a case study (2) on one organisation, the White and Yellow Cross Care Foundation (WYCCF) on Sint Maarten in the Caribbean. A case study is “*the preferred strategy when ‘how’ or ‘why’ questions are being posed, when the investigator has little control over events and when the focus is on a contemporary phenomenon within some real-life context*” (2, page 1). To determine the questions that are most significant for the research topic in the case, and to gain some precision in formulating these questions one can first review the literature on the topic (3). So, before formulating the research questions in this study a literature review was executed on ‘desired feedback culture’. For that purpose, a rapid review method was applied. Rapid reviews are a type of knowledge synthesis where elements of the systematic review process are condensed or left out in order to provide information quickly (4). In this case, the rapid review method from Virginia Commonwealth University (5) was used. It consists of seven steps, including identifying biases before planning and executing the search.

2.1. Biases and presumptions

Within the organisation WYCCF premises were uttered about differences between staff regarding the desired feedback culture. Before going into the details of the literature review, the author wants to share these intuitions and educated guesses on what the answers of the survey might be. Reason for making these predictions explicit are well described by Spear (6). Spear argues that true insights in research do not merely come from the information gathered and the outcomes and conclusions reached. It is understanding the gap between expectations and results that lead to the really valuable insights and where the real learning happens.

Within WYCCF there were two presumptions on feedback culture. Some managers expected differences in behaviour and desires regarding feedback from different ages. These notions are supported by numerous narratives on the internet and in the popular media, stating that every generation has its own perceptions, expectations, values and desires regarding the workplace that need to be managed well. Especially, representatives of the young generation Gen Z are supposed to have different desires in the working place and behave differently. They are even said to have different values than the rest of the staff.

Managers mentioned also cultural background as possible cause for different desires and actions. They expected Dutch-Caribbean staff members, Non-Dutch Caribbean staff members and Dutch staff members to express different desires regarding feedback culture.

2.2. Rapid review and research questions

The literature search was executed in Google Scholar on the key terms *desired feedback culture, age and culture*. After reading 50 abstracts, eight articles were selected to have a first and quick impression on feedback culture and the differences between age groups and cultures.

Age

Burlacu (7) did find that there is evidence of age differences in feedback reactions with younger (<40) adults being particularly concerned with information that will benefit them in the future and older adults (>40) being particularly concerned with information that conveys a positive relationship with one’s supervisor. Furthermore, Burlacu compared the United States with China, using Hofstede and concludes that “differences (particularly power distance differences and differences along the collectivistic/individualistic axis) can impact the way job performance is measured and appraised. They can especially impact employee perceptions of and reactions to performance feedback, as Chinese employees may feel that they do not have the right to appraise their supervisors’ evaluations negatively. For these reasons, cross-cultural considerations need to be taken into account when conducting organizational research”.

Gaidhani et al. (8) studied the attitude of Generation Z to the workplace and one of their conclusions was that they needed constant feedback from their mentors. Baker Rosa et al. (9) conducted 25 interviews with managers in the hospitality industry. They found that these managers state that Millennials desire ample, positive and personal feedback. However, the question is to what extent this is specific for Millennials. Simon et al. (10) e.g. gave seventeen college-aged (M = 18.9 years) and twenty-four healthy, older adults (M = 70.3 years) the probabilistic selection task, in which participants are trained on probabilistic stimulus outcome information and then tested to determine whether they learned more from positive or negative feedback. As a group, the old adults learned equally well from positive and negative feedback, whereas the college-aged group learned more from positive than negative feedback.

However, Rudolph et al. (11) studied ten myths regarding generational difference in organizational science. Myth #6 states that generations need to be managed at work. “..... research generally does not and cannot support the existence of generational differences, so there is nothing to “manage” in this regard. Organizations open themselves up to an unnecessary liability if they

manage individuals based on generational membership. The focus should be shifted toward managing perceptions of generations rather than generations themselves". A general statement by Rudolph et al. is that rather than focusing on simplified, rather deterministic groupings of people into generations, staff development occurs in a continuous, multicausal, multidirectional, and multidimensional process.

Also, Mlodzik and De Meuse (12) studied a possible existence of differences among the four generations (BabyBoomers, GenX, Millennials and GenZ) in the workforce today. Their review of the peer-reviewed literature found little scientific support for this claim. There appears to be many more similarities than differences across generations. Furthermore, they state that distinctions in national culture and unique historical experiences may create regional generational difference effects.

Cultures

Stone-Romero and Stone (13) found that there is a difference in how different cultures react to (negative) feedback. They say that self-enhancement tendencies are far more common among people in individualistic cultures than among people in collectivistic cultures.

In their study on newcomer feedback inquiry in organisations, Wolfe Morisson et al. (14) found that individuals from the United States reported more newcomer feedback inquiry than individuals from Hong Kong. This difference was related to cultural differences in self-assertiveness and power distance. These results suggest that some of the implicit assumptions about newcomer feedback seeking may be less valid outside of the US. In particular, newcomers within low-individualism and high-power distance societies may be less likely to rely on supervisor-focused feedback inquiry for reducing uncertainty and managing their performance. The research of MacDonald et al. (15) supports the premise that the motivation to seek performance feedback varies as a function of national culture. Compared to Canadians, image-defense motivation was more predictive of (a) the importance placed on feedback source, and (b) whether feedback is sought in public, for feedback-seeking decisions among Chinese participants. Ego-defense motivation was more predictive of the importance placed on feedback valence for feedback-seeking decisions among Canadian participants than among those from China.

Gender

One could argue that there also might be differences in the desired feedback culture, based on gender. Coffman and Klinowski (16) e.g. state, in contrast with other studies, that "women are no less eager to receive performance feedback than men". Because the group in this research consisted of 79 female staff members and just two males no sub question is answered regarding a possible relation between gender and desired feedback culture.

2.3. Research questions

The research is not about the impact of different cultural backgrounds, ages and genders on feedback culture. Nor it is about the importance of cultural diversity in the organisational feedback culture.

The main research question focuses on (differences in) *desired* feedback culture. This brought us to the following main research question *What is the feedback the WYCCF staff desires?* And two sub questions:

1. To what extent are there differences in the desired feedback culture in our healthcare organization, based on age?
2. To what extent are there differences in the desired feedback culture in our healthcare organisation, based on Place of Birth?
3. What does the desired feedback culture mean in terms of actions for the management of the organisation?

2.4. Survey

To answer the questions a questionnaire was designed. The questions were based on Buha (17) and can be found as an annex to this article. The questions were scored on a five-point scale from not at all, not, more or less, yes to very much. The questionnaire was tested in a group of eleven staff members and evaluated for its understanding, improvements have been made based on the suggestions. The final questionnaire was presented to staff members, participants of a one-day workshop *Co-creating a Feedback Culture*. Seven of these workshops have been organised. The staff was selected on function and availability. Only caregiving staff from st Martin's Home and Sister Basilia Centre were selected. The groups were mixed and representative for age, function, cultural background; different teams were brought together. Each workshop consisted of maximum 15 participants, in total 81 staff members filled in the questionnaire, all involved in the organisation's primary process. The total amount of staff at WYCCF is 194, the total of workers in the primary process is 141, meaning 57,45%.

That brings us to the case study research design as mentioned in **figure 1**.

Figure 1: Case study research design

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Demographic data of the questionnaire

All 81 participants in the workshop filled in the questionnaire. During the analysis it appeared that a few demographic data were missing. The group consisted of 32 nurses at different levels (nursing assistant, LNA, RNA); 27 group leaders, 5 unit leaders; 8 paramedic staff, including a psychologist, two other staff members. And six people did not answer the question regarding their function (see **Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Function

Regarding ages a distinction was made between (born between 1997 and 2012); Millennials (born between 1981 and 1996); GenX (born between 1965 and 1980) and Baby Boomers (born between 1946 and 1964). The distribution was as mentioned in **table 1** and **table 2**.

Gen Z	21
Millennials	31
GenX	25
BB	2
No answer	2
	81

Table 1: age distribution in numbers

Table 2: Age distribution graph

Regarding place of birth 14 different locations were mentioned, two people did not fill in this question. People from the Caribbean, being SXM, Dominica, StLucia, Curacao, Aruba, Grenada, Jamaica were grouped together. We counted The Netherlands and Guyana and Suriname as two different groups and added a group 'others'.

The distribution was as in **table 3**:

Dutch Caribbean	N=39, 48%
Non Dutch Caribbean	N=18, 22%
South America	N=12, 15%
NL	N=7, 9%
Others	N=3, 4%
Not	N=2, 2%

Table 3: Distribution place of birth in numbers

3.2. Results of the survey on desired feedback culture

On the actual desired feedback culture questions were asked about their values regarding feedback and the feedback process (see appendix 1).

3.2.1 Values

The scores for yes and very much were combined to a positive result. Five topics were valued by the great majority of the staff. Ninety nine percent of the participants answered positive to the question if they valued trust. Ninety eight percent gave a positive score on their valuing learning and development opportunities in their work. Ninetyseven percent of the participants answered yes or very much on the question if they valued recognition for their achievements. And 87% valued creativity in their work. And 81% valued autonomy positively. There are no significant differences between age and place of birth.

3.2.2. Feedback process

Ninety seven percent of the answers mention a preference for honest face-to-face feedback. There is no age difference here. This feedback may be given by someone younger than them (93%). Eighty one percent appreciate formal structured feedback, such as annual performance reviews. Seventy eight percent wants feedback to be backed up with evidence. However, also differences in the answers can be seen regarding the way feedback is given. Seventy three percent of the participants is positive about real-time feedback on the job. Fifty-nine percent expect feedback to be personalized, tailored to their goals. Those who do not expect that belong mostly to GenX and Millennials.

The respondents have a preference for feedback face-to-face (4.52 on a five point scale) and formal (4.12).

Only 35% answers yes or very much regarding the question, if feedback should be given frequently (e.g. weekly). When you look deeper into the answers of the 21% who does not or not at all want this; the resistance appears mainly in representatives from GenX and Millennials.

Also, regarding the question if they prefer to get feedback from multiple sources the answers are more divided. Fifty nine percent answers positive; thirty-two more or less and nine percent not or not at all. Three out of the five people who do not want this at all come from GenZ. However, when we look at GenZ as a whole 62% is positive, 24 % more or less and 14% not at all.

When we look at the moment feedback should be given, 58% states that they expect feedback to be given fast (same day). Five out of seven who do not want this or not at all come from GenZ. When we look at GenZ as a whole 52% expects so and 24% does not. Much lower scores were given as an answer to the question if the participants accept harsh (negative) feedback. Only 43% says yes or very much. Nineteen percent says not at all, these are all representatives from GenX or Millennials. GenZ gives 47% positive answers here, 24% negative. None of the 15 negative answers is from any of the Dutch participants here, only one from the Dutch Caribbean (see **figure 4**).

Figure 4: Harsh feedback

On the question if the participants are comfortable with using technology for feedback, 61% is positive, 17% negative. These negatives are spread over the age groups (also 3 out of 14 belong to GenZ). However, GenZ in general is 62% in favour of using technology, 14% is not. Again, none of the 6 negative scores is from a Dutch participant (see **figure 5**).

Figure 5: Technology

On the question, if people like feedback via digital platforms and games, the results are the most negative. 53% of all respondents says no or not at all, only 20% is positive. Two out of thirteen that answered not-at-all come from GenZ. However, half of the positive scores are also from GenZ. In general, 34% of GenZ is in favor of digital platforms and games, where 43% is not or even

not at all (9%). Only one of the fourteen answers not-at-all came from the Netherlands, 1 from South America; 2 from st-Maarten and the majority (9) came from Non-Dutch Caribbean (see **figure 6**: digital platforms and games).

Figure 6: Digital platforms and games

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Age

When we look at the first sub question *To what extent are there differences in the desired feedback culture in our healthcare organization, based on age?* we conclude that there are little differences. Rather we see that the respondents share general values, like trust, creativity, the need for learning and development, autonomy and recognition. Getting feedback from people from younger generations is said to be no problem. The participants in general do not like feedback to be given weekly; do not want it to be harsh and do not like technology or digital applications to be used. Although, GenZ does have the greatest preference for technology in general, there is little difference preference of GenZ for digital applications for feedback.

Based on the results we can conclude that this research confirms what has been argued by other scientists (7,11) about the myth regarding GenZ. The idea of Gaidhani et al. (10) who studied the attitude of GenerationZ to the workplace, that they GenZ staff needed constant feedback from their mentors is not confirmed by the data in this survey. Also, there is no indication that GenZ would relate different to harsh feedback than other age groups. The results do not support what is also mentioned in popular media. There is no significant proof for GenZ-representatives to be different from other age groups; within each age group there are great differences. So, managers at WYCCF might be too much influenced by popular media about specific desires of GenZ staff about feedback.

Place of birth

Regarding place of birth the literature also predicted differences. When we look at the second sub question *To what extent are there differences in the desired feedback culture in our healthcare organization, based on place of birth?* we conclude that again there are little differences. Maybe Dutch and Dutch-Caribbean staff members are more in favour of technology. And Dutch and Dutch-Caribbean claim to have less problems with harsh feedback. Dutch Caribbean staff members might have been largely influenced in this by the Dutch education system. Differences regarding feedback seeking were not found.

These results might be Caribbean specific. However, the explanation can also relate to how Hoffman and Verdooren (18) approach cultural differences. They strongly oppose to dividing people in cultural groups or cultural dimensions like Hofstede (19) and Trompenaars and Hampden-Turner (20) do. They call that 'culturalism' and promote to see the whole person rather than the person as a representative of a culture, which is just one of his characteristics. One's communication and behaviour not only depend on culture, but also on social, demographic and economic factors, that may be even more important. Like stated in the subtitle of the book: *Cultures do not meet, people do*. That might also be the main reason why the managers mentioned cultural background as possible cause for different desires and actions. They might be prejudiced about what people from different cultural backgrounds desire. Van Linden (21) states that a shared collective vision on feedback culture is important. Cooperation and shared values on the desired feedback culture are necessary to create a longlasting feedback culture, especially in diverse teams.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

When we look at the consequences for the third research question, what the implications are for the management of the organisation, we can conclude that no specific measures need to be taken for specific age groups or cultural background, caused by differences in desired feedback culture. That means we can rely on studies like Kahmann and Mulder (22) who generally conclude that creating

a feedback culture in organisations requires attention to both the quality of feedback and the importance placed on feedback within the organisation. They provide managers with the following practical suggestions:

1. Ensure high-quality feedback. The feedback should be continuous, open, specific, objective, fair and honest.
2. Emphasize the importance of feedback Managers and supervisors must serve as role models in seeking, giving, and using feedback. Feedback should be frequent, both formal and informal, and the organization should recognize and reward the act of giving and using feedback. The overall climate should support feedback as a valued and routine part of work.

Besides, the organisation can profit from the diversity of its staff. Diverse teams bring in general a variety of cultural, generational, and experiential backgrounds, which means feedback is informed by multiple viewpoints. This leads to more comprehensive and nuanced insights, helping individuals and the organization as a whole grow.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Annex Questionnaire on preferences for feedback

Function:

Age:

Place of birth:

Gender:

Question	Not at all	Not	More or less	Yes	Very much
1. Do you appreciate to get formal structured feedback, such as annual performance reviews?					
2. Do you value recognition for your achievements?					
3. Are you comfortable with receiving feedback from someone younger than you are?					
4. Are you comfortable with using technology for feedback?					
5. Do you prefer honest face-to-face feedback?					
6. Do you value autonomy in your work?					
7. Do you want frequent feedback (e.g weekly)?					
8. Do you want feedback to be backed by facts or evidence?					
9. Do you want real-time feedback and coaching (on the job)?					
10. Do you value learning and development opportunities in your work?					
11. Do you accept harsh feedback?					
12. Do you expect feedback to be personalized and tailored to your goals?					
13. Do you like feedback via digital platforms and games?					
14. Do you value creativity and innovation in your work?					
15. Do you expect feedback to be given fast ?					
16. Do you prefer to get feedback from multiple sources and perspectives?					
17. Do you value trust and fairness?					